

POLICY BRIEF

REVERSE THE DECLINE OF POLLINATORS BY JOINING FORCES WITH CITIZEN SCIENCE

How authorities should leverage citizen generated data and community actions to reverse the decline of pollinators

In a Nutshell

Academic research and citizen science have generated robust evidence showing the urgency of pollinator protection. The next step is clear: policy should evolve from commitments to collaborative action. Empowering citizen-led initiatives and soundly embedding them in policy frameworks can provide a pathway for reversing pollinator decline across the globe.

Policy context

Pollinator populations continue to decline globally, driven by factors such as habitat loss, soil degradation, pesticides and climate change. Still, public authorities often struggle to act effectively. Global and regional frameworks set ambitious targets: the UN's Global Biodiversity Framework (Target 7) calls for reducing pollution to levels that are not harmful to biodiversity; and the EU's Nature Restoration Regulation (Art. 10) aims to improve pollinator diversity and reverse population declines by 2030.

To reach these goals, urgent action is imperative. Pollinator protection is not only an environmental priority. It is an investment in sustainable development, food security, and societal well-being.

Policy challenge

Public authorities are left with a key challenge: how to move from commitments to impactful, coordinated action.

Decision making remains difficult as policymakers often face structural barriers: incomplete official monitoring schemes, fragmented data, and diversity of the many actors involved, from farmers and industry to scientists and civil society organizations.

Citizen science and community engagement can be pivotal to addressing these challenges, by strengthening knowledge and monitoring and fostering civil society engagement.

Citizens can make a difference

Citizen science already plays a crucial role in documenting pollinator decline worldwide. Citizen scientist initiatives help fill critical data gaps, support research and engage the public. In Europe, long-term Butterfly Monitoring Schemes rely heavily on volunteers.

They have also informed peer-reviewed studies and assessments, providing sample sizes impossible for academia and official monitoring alone

to achieve. Now we must urgently move to action. Citizen engagement can also help in policy design and implementation.

Research by more4nature shows that citizen science and action are essential for practical responses to pollinator decline, such as developing regenerative farming models and informing effective sustainable urban planning.

Course of Action →

As national authorities develop restoration plans and scale up action on pollinator protection, more4nature calls for collaborative efforts. Scientific evidence shows it delivers better outcomes¹. Including citizen generated data and community-led actions in joint governance efforts is key to conserving and restoring ecosystems across rural, peri-urban, and urban areas. Civil society can help to promote pollinator protection and to detect, report, and act on harmful practices, supporting authorities where capacity is limited.

We recommend that national and subnational authorities involved in pollinator restoration plans:

- Recognise and integrate citizen science expertise in policy processes, for example by opening expert committees and involving citizen organisations in the design of pollinator action plans. Portugal's national pollinator plan shows how co-production can improve feasibility and implementation.
- Provide sustainable funding for citizen science initiatives that raise awareness, monitor pollinators, promote compliance, and support enforcement of Article 10 of the Nature Restoration Regulation.

Voices on the ground

Portugal

Photo by Cândida Ramos

Eva Monteiro

President of the NGO Tagis – Centro de Conservação das Borboletas de Portugal and coordinator of the citizen science project Censos de Borboletas de Portugal

“Public authorities must mobilize citizens by building capacity through education and communication, fostering active and participatory engagement. Supporting pollinator monitoring schemes based on citizen science is essential to enhance public understanding of pollinators and promote their conservation. They are also crucial for designing and implementing policies that achieve the transformative societal changes needed to reverse pollinator decline.”

Reach out to us!

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¹ Deguines N, Julliard R, de Flores M, Fontaine C (2012) The Whereabouts of Flower Visitors: Contrasting Land-Use Preferences Revealed by a Country-Wide Survey Based on Citizen Science. PLoS ONE 7(9): e45822. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0045822>